

WEB 2.0 TOOLS: USE OF KAHOOT TO REDUCE THE SPELLING MISTAKES AMONG B.TECH LEARNERS OF COMMUNICATIVE ENGLISH

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Abstract:

B.Tech learners of Communicative English are inclined towards technology and hardly focus on spellings in their writing. Today, students are called as netizens or net generations (Educause.edu, 2016) due to their over usage of web tools. My paper explores strategies to reduce spelling mistakes in B.Tech learners of Communicative English by introducing games using Kahoot, in the class. In the empirical design approach, the questions framed by the teacher would help the learner identify the correct spelling through game based learning. Though the learners face technical challenges, learning through games is very interesting.

Key Words: Net Generation, Kahoot, Undergraduates of Engineering & Spellings

Hypothesis:

The Engineering undergraduates who are interested in anything with internet would learn correct spelling through game based e-learning.

Introduction:

Most of the teachers find it challenging to teach spellings to students at undergraduate level. Due to heterogeneous educational background, many students are unable to spell the words right in their academic writing. This has affected their career growth. As technical students are inclined towards technology, teaching-learning process using web 2.0 tools becomes more compatible. Introducing Quizzes through Kahoot which is a game based LMS motivates and engages students and a positive impact develops in the learning process in them.

Rabail Tahir in his research investigated the effect of using Kahoot in his classroom. He focused on learning performance, classroom dynamics, students' and teachers' attitudes and perceptions, and student anxiety. Through his qualitative and quantitative research with 93 students, he found Kahoot to have a positive effect in teaching and learning process. He felt technical hitches, time stress and fear of losing the game were the challenges the students faced.

The method is to design a game based questionnaire where students would respond using the Kahoot! Kahoot! is a game-based student response system (GSR) where the classroom is temporarily transformed into a game show where the teacher is the game show host, and the students are the contenders (Wang, 2015)¹. The teacher frames some quiz questions and creates the game using Kahoot! The students would respond to them. Some conceptual questions that would test their retention and spelling ability will be asked in the game as a quiz. The students have an option to redo their wrong questions. In this process the students identify their mistakes and learn the correct spelling. Kahoot! The game-based application is very interesting and easy to create and motivating to play games in the classroom. Multiple choice questions or true or false type questions can be asked using Kahoot. The background music while playing the game not only triggers enthusiasm in students but also keeps them alert throughout the game. This enhances students' concentration and keeps them focused on what they are supposed to do. Above all, playing games break the monotony of the traditional classroom and makes a learner centred class. The results would be based on score of every individual. It would be number of questions answered correctly in the given time. Based on the score the ability of the student would be analysed and the teacher would plan further quizzes based on the responses.

Samples/Population:

40 students of III year Mechanical Engineering of whom only 19 could participate.

Method:

To test the spellings, I have framed 10 questions on the topic Presentation skills. The questions were to review the lesson and also to test the spelling ability in the learner. Four options were given to answer each question. Three of the four options had wrong spelling that would sound similar. The learner needs to comprehend the question, recollect the answer and identify the answer with its correct spelling. Of 40 students in the class only 19 could participate as few did not have an extra device to play, few had problem with the connectivity and few others had no technical knowledge. Of 19 participants only 17 were able to answer as the other two could not match the speed of the game as the game has fixed time to answer each question. This gave

a great learning experience in the learners and a positive outlook for enhancing their mental ability as well as technical skills.

Questions With the Options Created on Kahoot:

Q1. This is one of the types of oral presentation.

- a. impromptu **b. impromptu** c. impromptu d. impromptu

Q2. Presentation skills are very essential for ones _____ growth.

- a. professional b. profesional **c. professional** d. professional

Q3. An advertising informative paper/document in a template on a folded leaflet is _____.

- a. broture b. brosure c. brocher **d. brochure**

Kahoot! is a game that requires two gadgets/devices to play. One gadget to see the questions and the other to answer. Offline, one device per student would be sufficient to play the game as the questions would be projected on the screen, in the class. But, if it is played online, the student needs to have two gadgets, one for the questions screen and the other to answer. The teacher creates multiple choice questions or true /false questions and hosts the game. Students log in through Kahoot! it using another device and enter the game with a game pin given by the host, which is automatically generated by the app/system. Each question is displayed on the screen for thirty seconds and options are given in four boxes with different colours, say Red, Blue, Green and Yellow. The participant reads the question and options given on the screen and press the colour/box in his device to answer. After 30 seconds, the screen displays the correct answer. This helps the learner to know if he has answered it correct or not. In this process s/he learns the correct spelling. It is easy for the teacher to evaluate each student immediately. The app displays the graph of number of correct answers along with the time taken to answer each question by each participant/learner. This assessment is done after each question and also after the game is completed. The winners or the top three scores would be displayed and applauded. This motivates and builds confidence in each student. It is also challenging for other students to score better in the next game.

The major challenge in every participant was a sort of anxiety of losing the game due to time constraint was constantly observed. This has to be overcome by every learner. The other challenges were, the learners had to stay focussed throughout the game as they had to concentrate on question, answer and the colour of the box on the other device.

Discussion:

Students get motivated and get engaged in learning the unknown words and their spelling. Relatively this game based learning gives a positive effect on the learning ability of the student. It improves the class attendance, lessens the late arrivals to the class and higher usage of dictionary app. The students develop concentration and learn time management. This helps the learners to fair well in competitive exams and interviews/placements. In spite of showing improved academic results it has its own challenges like anxiety in students, technical issues etc.

Conclusions:

The Teaching learning process goes on uninterrupted with a positive and favourable results from students. Yet there would be some technical glitches like students from rural background may not be aware of using the technology, having extra device/gadget, poor connectivity, and time constraint would be the challenges in responding to the answers through kahoot!

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